

A COMMON, OPEN SOURCE INTERFACE
BETWEEN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA
INFRASTRUCTURES AND FRONT-END
APPLICATIONS

Deliverable 17

Version 1.0 from 2019/07/31

openEO full API implementation, first version

Change history

Issue	Date	Author(s)	Description
0.1	2019/07/24	Matthias Mohr, WWU	First draft.
0.2	2019/07/30	Matthias Schramm, TU Wien	Internal review; updating section 1
1.0	2019/07/31	Matthias Schramm, TU Wien	Final review and adaptation for submission

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List of Acronyms

API Application Programming Interface

EO Earth Observation

GDAL Geospatial Data Abstraction Library

JSON JavaScript Object Notation

OGC Open Geospatial Consortium

PoC Proof-of-Concept

STAC SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog

UDF User Defined Function

WCS OGC Web Coverage Service

WFS OGC Web Feature Service

WKT OGC Well-Known Text representation of coordinate reference systems

WMS OGC Web Map Service

WMTS OGC Web Map Tile Service

WPS OGC Web Processing Service

1 Executive summary

The openEO project develops an open Application Programming Interface (API) to connect R, Python and JavaScript clients to big Earth Observation (EO) cloud back-ends in a simple and unified way. This deliverable summarises the API's development since the submission of deliverable D04 [1] and complements the online API documentation [2]. Since that public documentation is updated regularly, this report will mainly summarise the actual state of the API. For more detailed descriptions, please refer to the online documentation.

This deliverable is accompanied by two other project deliverables (D18: First versions of back-end drivers; D20: First versions of three front-end drivers). During the project's run the original idea of designing a three-layered-openEO API was rejected (see deliverable 13 [3], section 7.1, where this strategy and its needed requirements is still described as an alternative). Therefore, the planned content of this report was changed. Instead of describing a core layer of the openEO API, it focuses on the openEO specifications, which are mainly implemented with the OpenAPI standard and additional human-readable textual explanations.

2 openEO API

While the latest version of the documentation is accessible via [2], older versions are available in the GitHub repository¹. It consists of following different parts:

- Written documentation explaining terms and concepts, including a 'getting started' section and development guidelines.
- OpenAPI²-based API specification for the HTTP-based openEO Core API
- AsyncAPI³-based specification for the WebSocket-based openEO Subscriptions API
- Process reference

The openEO processes⁴ are developed and released independently⁵, but their most recent version is also packaged and released together with the API.

In general, the API has the following set of functionalities.

- Basic functionality, including discovery of API features, processes and collections.
- Authentication, either OpenID Connect or HTTP Basic
- On-the-fly processing / previews
- Batch processing, including estimates for processing costs
- Secondary web services, primarily for viewing and downloading results
- Process graph validation

¹<https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-api>

²<https://www.openapis.org/>

³<https://www.asyncapi.com/>

⁴<http://processes.openeo.org>

⁵<https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-processes>

D17: full API implementation, 1st version

- Process graph storage
- File storage
- User Defined Functions (UDFs)
- Subscriptions for notifications and monitoring

2.1 Version history

Since the Proof-of-Concept (PoC) in March 2018, the following versions of the API have been released:

- 0.3.0 (Sep 2018): Major rework [4]
- 0.3.1 (Nov 2018): Corrections and clarifications [5]
- 0.4.0 (Mar 2019): Improved discovery, added process catalogue [6], new process graph structure and improvements based on developer feedback [7]
- 0.4.1 (May 2019): Corrections and clarifications [8]
- 0.4.2 (Jul 2019, latest): Corrections and clarifications [9]

2.2 Changes since the proof of concept

Although the structure of the API hasn't changed very much on the first look, there were substantial changes between the PoC and the current version. As the change log and many details are very technical, the most important changes will be described in the following paragraphs.

The most important change was the introduction of an extensive set of common processes [6]. Although not directly part of the API, the processes had a big impact on the API specification as e.g. the process discovery was extended [6]. Also a new process graph was introduced, describing the workflow of algorithms using the openEO processes. The original PoC did not allow to split and merge the workflow into parallel tasks, but only enabled step-by-step execution. By introducing a dependency graph structure for the process graphs, this problem was solved. It also supports callbacks (see figure 2.1) and therefore a more fine granular specification of the processes. Process graph variables improve the interoperability of process graphs when exchanged between back-ends.

Since the PoC the whole openEO API aims to be compatible with OGC API - Commons so that it can be well integrated with the next generation of OGC API standards. The data discovery endpoints are already compliant to SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC)⁶ and OGC API - Features (formerly known as OGC Web Feature Service (WFS) 3).

Other notable changes / additions:

- Service discovery via well-known document as defined in RFC 5785 [10].
- Service metadata such as versions, title and description.

⁶<http://stacspec.org>

- Billing plans and budgets that allow charging users.
- Authentication via OpenID Connect⁷.
- Process graph validation.
- Estimates regarding costs, volume and time for batch processing of jobs.
- WebSocket-based Subscription API for notifications and monitoring.

Figure 2.1: Visualisation of a new process graph with callbacks (yellow).

2.3 Remarks on the use of standards

Whenever possible the openEO API is designed to incorporate existing standards and specifications.

- Service discovery via well-known document uses RFC 5785 [10].
- The openEO API doesn't expose viewing services directly, but back-ends are free to expose data holdings and/or processing results using standards such as OGC Web Map Service (WMS), OGC Web Map Tile Service (WMTS), OGC Web Coverage Service

⁷<https://openid.net/connect/>

(WCS) or their respective OGC API successors. For processing results these services can be published via the openEO secondary web services interface. For data holdings the openEO API uses STAC, which is based on OGC API - Features and therefore also bases on OGC API - Commons. Therefore, other standards such as OGC API - Coverages can be exposed through the same interface.

- The API documentation uses RFC 2119 [11].
- The API specification uses OpenAPI and AsyncAPI.
- The API follows the HTTP/1.1 standard as specified in RFC 7230 [12] and RFC 7231 [13].
- Web Linking as defined in RFC 5998 [14] is used throughout the API.
- HTTP requests and responses are mostly encoded in JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) as defined in RFC 7159 [15].
- Temporal data is encoded using RFC 3339 [16] and/or ISO 8601 [17] respectively.
- Currencies are defined using ISO 4217.
- Authentication should primarily use OpenID Connect. HTTP Basic (RFC 7617 [18]) is also supported.
- Vector data / features can be encoded in GeoJSON (RFC 7946 [19]).
- JSON Schema (IETF draft⁸) is used to define and validate process parameters and process return values. There are currently thoughts about supporting only a subset of JSON Schema to simplify the process specification⁹ and therefore lower the implementation effort.
- File Formats and options are recommended to be aligned with the Geospatial Data Abstraction Library (GDAL)¹⁰. We use standardised file formats such as GeoTiff and netCDF whenever possible.
- Projections are communicated either by EPSG codes¹¹ or PROJ definition¹². OGC Well-Known Text representation of coordinate reference systems (WKT) 2¹³ is planned to be supported once it is released.
- It is planned to support either remoteStorage (IETF draft¹⁴) or the Amazon S3 specification¹⁵ for file management in the future. Decisions about the next steps will be made once the final directions of the remoteStorage specification can be assessed.

Other standards were also considered, notably OGC Web Processing Service (WPS). The biggest barrier for its adoption is the lack of a standardised way to chain processes into full workflows.

⁸<https://json-schema.org/specification-links.html#draft-7>

⁹<https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-processes/issues/64>

¹⁰<https://gdal.org/>

¹¹<http://www.epsg.org/>

¹²<https://proj.org/>

¹³<https://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/wkt-crs>

¹⁴<https://tools.ietf.org/html/draft-dejong-remotestorage-13>

¹⁵<https://docs.aws.amazon.com/s3/index.html>

2.4 State of the API and Future Work

The API's development went through several iterations and is working well for most use cases. Although the functionality is already quite extensive, some parts of the API still need to prove their flexibility in practice as only few partners have implemented them yet. This includes authentication with OpenID Connect, deployment of secondary web services, UDFs, the Subscription API and file management (see below). Until the end of the project's funding period, focus will be on the improvement of these listed aspects. For file management, the rudimentary API is planned to be replaced by either remoteStorage or Amazon S3, if a stable and well-supported standard evolves during the project period. Additionally, we will update all integrated external standards and specifications once new versions are released. This is likely to happen for STAC, OGC APIs and JSON Schema. The new process graph definition will require some more fine-tuning, too. All other parts of the API are well tested and implemented by several partners to have evidence of a good specification. Additionally, a strong focus will be to increase interoperability between back-ends.

The next version of the openEO API is planned to be the final version 1.0. Its development will include the involvement of the project's pilot users to help the timely identification of potential flaws in the API. Additional issues and planned improvements towards the final version are listed and discussed constantly in the public GitHub issue tracker¹⁶.

The first version of the openEO processes is currently implemented by back-ends and clients. Therefore, it is likely that adjustments need to be made based on feedback from implementers. A list of potential changes and additions is available in the GitHub issue tracker of the repository containing the processes¹⁷.

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